
Teachers' Perceptions about Environmental Management Indoor Learning at Pembina 1 Bantan State Kindergarten.

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ABSTRACT: Teacher perception is the process of receiving information in the form of opinions or responses that are born through a process of observation and experience and then interpreted in order to create learning that suits needs. Indoor Learning Environment Management is part of the process of coordinating various environmental components that can influence facilities properly. An indoor learning environment or what can also be called an indoor learning room is a place where children study inside a building. This research aims to find out how teachers perceive the management of the indoor learning environment and to find out what efforts teachers perceive in optimizing the management of the indoor learning environment at the Pembina 1 Bantan State Kindergarten. The number of respondents in this study was 14 respondents using a non-probability sampling technique, namely purposive sampling. This type of research is descriptive quantitative research with data collection techniques in the form of questionnaires and documentation. It was found that the teacher's perception regarding the management of the indoor learning environment at the Pembina 1 Bantan State Kindergarten was said to be very good because it was at a percentage interval of 81.78% for the teacher perception variable (X) and 81.80% for the Indoor Learning Environment Management variable.

KEYWORDS: Teacher Perceptions, Management of Indoor Learning Environments

INTRODUCTION

Perception is an action in the form of an opinion or attitude which in the process is preceded by sensing, in the form of a stimulus that enters and is received by the individual's receptor apparatus, namely the senses. The sense organs possessed by an individual are a link between the individual and his external world. Perception is the process of stimuli that are sensed by an individual, organized, then interpreted so that the individual realizes and understands what has been sensed. So it can be said that perception is a process related to the entry of messages or information into the brain of individual humans. Perception is an individual's integrated state of the stimulus they receive. All kinds of forms that exist within the individual, thoughts, feelings, experiences of the individual will actively influence the process of perception¹.

The perception of early childhood education (PAUD) teachers is a process of opinion or response by PAUD teachers which is based on the teacher's knowledge, ability to think, feelings and experiences, which are individual in nature². The environment is a place that can influence the process of human growth. In the context of children's learning, the environment should be well organized in order to create an atmosphere conducive to learning³. Management of the learning environment in the classroom (indoor) is one of the factors that can influence the growth and development of students, because the process of a child's growth and development for the first time at school occurs when the child is within the scope of the classroom environment where he is studying.

Learning environment management is the teacher's effort to create an active, effective, productive and efficient learning environment and is able to provide motivation to students to be able to study well so that students' potential can develop optimally⁴. There are targets in the process of managing the indoor learning environment, starting with how to identify the position or existence of the room that the child will later use as a place to study. At least, things of concern include the room, direction of the room,

¹ Setyo Nugroho, "Profesionalisme Guru SD Negeri Se-Kecamatan Warungasem Kabupaten Batang Suatu Tinjauan Aspek Persepsi Guru Tentang Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah Dan Motivasi Berprestasi Guru," Jurnal Varidika Vol 24, No. 2 (2012).

² Prety Citra Pratesi, "Persepsi Guru PAUD Terhadap Faktor-Faktor Yang Menghambat Dalam Melaksanakan Pembelajaran Di PAUD Se- Kecamatan Ujan Mas Kabupaten Kepahian," Jurnal Pendidikan Islam Anak Usia Dini Vol. 2. No. 2 (2019): h.75

³ Ismail Wahyuni et al., "Pengelolaan Lingkungan Pembelajaran Di PAUD Kemala Bayangkari." Vol. 2. No.2 (2019): h.123.

⁴ Ardhi Hidayat, "Manajemen Pengelolaan Kelas Di Paud," DIMAR: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam Anak Usia Dini Vol. 3. No. 1 (2021):h. 59.

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condition of the walls, condition of the floor, condition of the roof and other things that are needed in managing the learning environment⁵.

Classrooms for early childhood need to be designed to be fun. The use of bright colors so that it displays a cheerful effect is very popular with children. Sunlight should be able to shine and enter properly so that the class is not dark. Develop the classroom as a learning environment. This means that wherever the child faces, he learns⁶. A true teacher is not a figure who is only able to convey learning material, but what is more important is being able to instill exemplary values in students. If the teacher succeeds in building good interactions through good classroom management, then students with their abilities will be able to assess the quality of the teacher's personality⁷.

Managing the indoor learning environment is something that every early childhood education teacher should know in order to be able to manage the students' learning environment well. A well-managed classroom can be seen through effective classroom management, this is characterized by how individuals carry out the process of establishing, maintaining and restoring the classroom environment through effective ways of teaching and learning⁸. However, what happens in the field is that a small number of teachers cannot manage the learning environment well, and cannot create and maintain optimal learning room conditions. This is characterized by a lack of teacher skills to establish and maintain optimal classroom conditions and restore them when things happen that disturb the comfortable classroom atmosphere. Such as when preparing media and game tools that are dangerous for children. Apart from that, the management of the classroom (indoor) learning environment is still less focused and incomplete. As in the final activity in classroom management, there were still inappropriate table arrangements, media and whiteboard placement.

Not only that, other phenomena are that a small number of teachers are apathetic and do not play an active role. Most teachers think that managing the (indoor) learning environment has no important effect on the quality of learning. This is indicated by teachers who have not been able to make decisions or strategies to use when problems occur. This problem arose when the Puskesmas health team visited it directly. Where there are still some classes that have problems regarding classroom maintenance that is not in accordance with children's learning outcomes, such as classroom atmosphere, classroom conditions and classroom safety for young children.

Based on this phenomenon, it encouraged researchers to choose the title "**Teachers' Perceptions Regarding Management of the Indoor Learning Environment in the Pembina 1 Banten State Kindergarten**", as an interesting topic to discuss.

METHODS

This research uses survey research methods, this type of research is quantitative research, which means this research can be measured and calculated directly. This research uses a descriptive approach. Quantitative methods are research methods that are based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative or statistical in nature with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses⁹.

Population is the total (number) of subjects or sources of research data. The population of this study was 17 educators (teachers) and education staff. This research uses a non-probability sampling technique. This is a sampling or respondent technique that does not provide equal opportunities for each element or member of the population to be selected as a sample¹⁰. Data collection techniques use questionnaires and documentation. Data Analysis Techniques use Data Quality Tests by carrying out Validity Tests and Reliability Tests, Descriptive Statistical Analysis by using a Likert scale.

⁵ Rita Maryana, Nugraha, Ali, and Yeni Rachmawati, *Pengelolaan Lingkungan Belajar*, 4th ed. (Jakarta: Prenada Media, 2018), h. 34

⁶ Dadan Suryana, *Stimulasi & Aspek Perkembangan Anak*, 2nd ed. (Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group, 2019), h.231.

⁷ Ani Fitriana, "*Manajemen Pengelolaan Kelas Di TK Kartika II-26 Bandar Lampung*" (Universitas Negeri Raden Intan Bandar Lampung, 2018),h. 7.

⁸ Dewi Isti Qoma, Baharuddin Risyak, and Maman Surahman, "*Persepsi Guru Dalam Mengelola Ruang Kelas PAUD*," *Jurnal Pendidikan Anak* Vol 2, No. 1 (2016): h. 2.

⁹ Sugiyono, *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, Dan R&D*, 23rd ed. (Bandung: Alfabeta, CV, 2016), h. 14

¹⁰ *ibid.* h 122

Table 1 Likert Scale Value Weights

No	Alternative Answer	Value
1	Always	5
2	Often	4
3	Sometimes	3
4	Almost Never	2
5	Never	1

To determine the percentage, researchers used the formula $P = F/N \times 100\%$

Information

P = Number of percentages

F = Frequency

N = Number of respondents

The answer results are categorized as good (75% - 100%)

The answer results are categorized as sufficient (60% - 75%)

The answer results are categorized as poor (0% - 60%)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Creating an effective and enjoyable learning environment for students is an obligation that must be implemented and carried out by teachers. Because in reality, teachers are the most important part of the components that can produce success through learning that takes place in the classroom.

To be able to create an effective and enjoyable learning environment for students, teachers should have a good perception of young children themselves, understand their growth process and understand all their needs. So that students will feel safe, comfortable and happy when carrying out the learning process provided by the teacher.

Perception in communication science is called the core of communication because if our perception is inaccurate, it is impossible for us to communicate effectively. Perception is what determines whether we choose one message and ignore other messages¹¹. We as social creatures will always interact and socialize with various kinds of things that we will discover. And from there we will be able to interpret or perceive something.

Perception is a thought process experienced by every human individual through the process of selecting, organizing, interpreting and interpreting all input information received through the senses of sight, hearing, smell, touch, feeling and appreciation so as to produce a meaningful picture of everything that exists in this world.

According to the formulation known as stimulus-response (SR) theory, perception is one part of the overall process of the individual that produces a response after stimulation is applied to humans¹². Perception occurs through several processes, namely when a person faces an object, the individual will not provide feedback or reaction without the process being carried out. This is because when an individual sees a particular object, then indirectly, whether consciously or not, each individual's sensory organs will work and process the object starting from the senses, then to the brain and then the individual can feel feedback or provide a reaction in the form of behavior towards it. objects and stimuli.

Early childhood learning processes generally occur inside and outside the classroom. It all depends on how the teacher manages the surrounding environment so that it can be used as a place for learning. The environment has an important role and occupies a major position in building children's abilities and behavior.

Thus, providing a conducive environment is the most important implication so that children can learn and improve all aspects of their growth and development. Learning environment management is part of a process of coordinating and integrating various environmental components that can influence changes in children's behavior so that it can be well facilitated. Environmental management is very important to be realized as a form of responsibility in an effort to improve the quality of students in the process of learning activities to think imaginatively, exploratively and innovatively¹³. An indoor learning environment is a learning environment that is common and exists in every school so that it can be used by students as a learning resource or learning environment within the school. This learning environment can be a library, laboratory, auditorium and primarily a classroom.

Management of the indoor learning environment is the process of arranging or arranging the time, place and atmosphere of learning located in a building or classroom. An indoor learning environment is a learning environment that has been provided by

¹¹ Alex Sobur, *Psikologi Umum* (Bandung: Pustaka Setia, 2013), h. 385.

¹² Sobur, *Psikologi Umum*, h. 386.

¹³ Hasan et al., *Pengelolaan Lingkungan Belajar*, h.15.

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the school management which will be used by students as a learning resource or environment within the school¹⁴. The environment mainly has elements that provide a number of stimuli or incentives for students that need attention and need to be created in such a way, so that they can provide objects according to the child's needs and development.

Therefore, the need for careful planning, the accuracy of the learning environment will directly and indirectly greatly influence the learning process and outcomes that students will achieve. Ideally, the process of managing the learning environment is a combination of two things, namely superior teachers who are adequate in their knowledge and experience, and equipped with rooms with equipment that suits the development needs and interests of students¹⁵. Several things that teachers must pay attention to when planning selected activities for children is to prepare a learning environment through various stimulating and challenging activities, although this does not mean that they have to be equipped with complete equipment¹⁶.

In order to be able to design a PAUD environment that requires philosophical thinking, a number of artistic aspects are needed that are appropriate to the existing space and land as well as the needs for use in learning. In this way, the arrangement of the learning environment for early childhood is not only beautiful to the eye, but also functions optimally without reducing the beauty of the environment. The principles in question include: harmony, balance, beauty, artistic arrangement, economic value, safety and unity¹⁷.

Each research statement item is calculated using the product moment correlation formula. According to Sugiyono, the instrument is said to be valid if the correlation coefficient value of the item score with the total score is $r > 0.30$, conversely it is invalid if the correlation coefficient value of the item score with the total score is < 0.30 . The validity test used in this research is by using Product Moment or Pearson, with the help of the SPSS 25.0 For Windows program. The reliability test used is the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, which is useful for measuring the extent to which the question items asked reflect the same construct. An instrument can be said to be reliable if the test shows $\alpha > 0.60$.

The results of data processing regarding the reliability test show that variable Based on the instrument table regarding the teacher perception questionnaire which was distributed to 14 respondents, it can be concluded that the teacher perception at the Pembina 1 Banten State Kindergarten is included in the very good category, namely 81.78%. instrument regarding the indoor learning environment management questionnaire which was distributed to 14 respondents, it can be concluded that the management of the indoor learning environment at the Pembina 1 Banten State Kindergarten is included in the very good category, namely 81.80%.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis data that has been described, the researcher can conclude that:

- 1) The teacher's perception regarding the management of the indoor learning environment at the Pembina 1 Banten State Kindergarten is said to be very good because it is at a percentage interval of 81.78% for the teacher perception variable (X) and 81.80% for the indoor learning environment management variable. Even though the respondents' dominant answers were in the often and always categories, there were still a small number of teachers who perceived learning environment management at intervals on a sometimes scale.
- 2) The teacher's efforts in optimizing the management of the indoor learning environment at the Pembina 1 Banten State Kindergarten can be said to be good. This can be seen through the percentage test results for each statement instrument. It is clear that teachers are in the dominant category often and always in an effort to optimize the management of the indoor learning environment.

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¹⁴ Baiti Noor, "Konsep Pengelolaan Desain Lingkungan Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini," *Jurnal Kajian Pendidikan Dasar Dan Anak Usia Dini* Vol. 3 No. 1 (2020): h. 32

¹⁵ Asmidar Parapat, *Strategi Pembelajaran Anak Usia Dini Panduan Bagi Orang Tua, Guru, Mahasiswa, Dan Praktisi PAUD*, 1st ed. (Jawa Barat: EDU PUBLISHER, 2020), h. 165

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, h. 167

¹⁷ Siti Misra Susanti, "Manajemen Pengelolaan Lingkungan Belajar PAUD Berbasis Masyarakat," *Jurnal Tumbuh Kembang* Vol 5, No. 1 (2018): h. 5.

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